

MANAGEMENT PROVISIONS FOR TECHNOLOGICAL ACCESS TOWARDS EFFECTIVE PERFORMANCE: IMPLICATION FOR TEACHERS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The time of the 21st century is frequently viewed as a period of technology. Technology today, assumes a significant job, particularly that our instructive frameworks are confronting an episode prompting unfathomable aftermaths. The effect of technology can be felt in each conceivable field and one of such is in Education. To support, this study determined the technological access and its management provisions which assessed its effect on the teaching performance of the teachers. The use of descriptive correlational research design through random sampling technique with a survey questionnaire led to achieving the objectives of the study participated by 163 public elementary school teachers in San Francisco District, Division of San Pablo. The result showed a significant relationship between teacher respondents' technological access and the teaching performance which implies that the use of technological access helped teachers in improving their performance in the teaching and learning process together with its management provisions. This indicates that from poor to low level in teaching domains such as content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement and personal growth and professional development, they were able to reach a very satisfactory to an excellent level of performance. Also, the use of management provisions for technological access motivates the teachers to enhance their approaches and methodologies in teaching. The study suggests that the use of technological access and its management provisions significantly affect the teaching performance which promotes a high-performance level in the educative process.

Keywords: Management Provisions, Technological Access, Teaching Performance